

Comparison of the Aesthetic Pleasure Design Cultures between the East and the West

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Abstract

From the cultural perspective, aesthetic pleasure is influenced by the implicit and explicit ethnic characteristics. For instance, the triggers of laughter in western and eastern humors are different. The concepts of designing the aesthetic pleasure of a product may also be influenced by human lifestyles. Based on Aesthetic of Reception proposed by Hans Robert Jauss, this study attempted to use the fundamental framework of aesthetic pleasure which includes three perspectives, including creation (poiesis) , perception (aesthesis) , and purification (catharsis) , to examine the difference between western instrumentalism and eastern spiritualism. From the idea that creation is to produce aesthetic experience and is the representation of design, the development of the representation of design in the east and the west could be derived. Perception is the pleasant emotions created after affective reception. It is the perception of design that reflects the perceptions of pleasure in the eastern and the western world. Purification is the result of interactions with aesthetic experience, allowing us to understand the formation of taste and style. Through the fundamental framework of aesthetic pleasure, the difference between the east and the west in aesthetic pleasure can be more easily observed, and a new discourse of design can also be formed from this cultural perspective.

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Introduction

Eastern design thinking is different to Western viewpoint because of cultural difference, thus impacts the aesthetic characterization of design, therefore such as Eastern viewpoint of leaving blank, natural accessibility, animism, Yin and Yang harmonism, so as to negative and concealed subtractive aesthetic etc., some seem to be passive, apathetic design attitude, but after deeply thinking of Eastern design thought, it was found echoing to ROE (Return on emotion) addressed by John Maeda (2007), that is from simple life→slow life→rich life→happy life. Generally speaking, Eastern design thinking is of extreme flexibility, and especially focuses on the emotional demand of users, not only pays attention to the interfacial interaction between people, but also between people and objects, just like Japanese kanji “ai chaku”, “ai” means love, “chaku” means attach to, that is the symbiotic affection between human and objects, generates deep emotional cling, therefore no matter of design form or thing’s quantity, all result in “Just enough is good enough”, which means simple is meaningful. This concise viewpoint has also been tremendously applied by Western designers, for example, i-pod designer Jonathan Ive believes nihility is concrete, concept of enabling nihility to form entity. As previously mentioned Japanese kanji “ai chaku”, talks about the symbiotic affection between human and objects, and generates emotional cling, this is also what said by Toshiyuki Kita (2002), in addition to form and function, should add in third key element - soul, that is Japanese cultural viewpoint - “animism”. Therefore aesthetic pleasure is just tightly related to “ai chaku” viewpoint, because the spirit and meaning owned by objects make users generate emotional link, and extend the conservation time for objects.

Meaning behind aesthetic pleasure

During recent years, aesthetic studies has been not so focused on philosophical thinking as previous, or just probe into visual beauty, but rather like many research disciplines, agreed by mere coincidence, have moved research face toward emotional exploration, or define aesthetic as the perceptual response which makes people feel pleasant. Generally, in addition to aesthetic, things should also be meaningful and enable user to generate emotional link, even shape personal expression of taste and style, to achieve the function of social communication. So link between product aesthetic and emotional connection a hot topic, can even be define as “catering to the purpose and meaning conveyed by object, enable people to experience, enjoy, and imagine within it, generate aesthetic pleasure, and be able to generate fun to share with human”, this is the fundamental meaning of aesthetic pleasure. Many relevant literatures about the definition of emotion, pleasure, or experience tend to non-functional, non-rational, and

non-cognitive analysis, therefore this study defines aesthetic pleasure as sensationalism, that is quality sense “Qualia” (quality of feeling) called by Idei (2003), which is interaction between human and objects, the emotional response with pleasant visual and hearing from what is felt, experienced, that is sensationalism of beauty experiencing.

Lewis (1998) addressed that there are 2 categories of pleasure: one is the pleasure generated because desire is satisfied, which is pleasure of appreciation, its source is not ourselves, but the thing itself which induces emotion; the other one has nothing to do with desire, is related to the essence which induces pleasure, this is need pleasure. If compare with the pleasure categorization between Lewis and Jordon’s (2003) 4 categories: physio-pleasure, socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure, and ideo pleasure, it can be said that physio-pleasure is corresponding to Lewis’ need pleasure, while socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure, and ideo pleasure is corresponding to Lewis’ pleasure of appreciation, aesthetic pleasure belongs to the domain of appreciation pleasure, because aesthetic pleasure especially emphasizes on the purpose and meaning conveyed by object (might be intentional or purposive, but can also be the context imagined, experienced, or felt by users), then generate emotion with pleasant visual and hearing. Particular for other-culture aesthetic pleasure, often because of different cultural viewpoints on custom, habit, religion or life style, generates different aesthetic pleasure in terms of characterization or cognition, however, if further probe into cultural content construction or the meaning it represents, instead, it is easy to generate distant looking fascination on other-culture, even an interest of expecting infection, thus the design cultural comparison between Eastern and Western aesthetic pleasure would help to peep the difference of aesthetic pleasure.

Aesthetic pleasure framework

Responding to above analysis on aesthetic pleasure, it is found that there are matching points with Hans Robert Jauss’ aesthetic of reception, because Hans Robert Jauss’ research center is the interaction between work and reader, and the process of work accepted by reader, although aesthetic of reception has been widely applied in literature domain, but Hans Robert Jauss’ uses literature to communicate and probe the inter-influential relationship between viewer, work and the author, corresponding to the aesthetic pleasure within design communication, isn’t it also the inter-influential relationship between user-object-designer? Especially Wolfgang Iser (1978) extended Hans Robert Jauss to move artistic experience subject to reader, and addressed the communication structure of interaction between text and reader, even proposed that text value must rely on the creative reading of reader, evaporate reader’s imagination and fill up blank to concretize it, so as to construct text meaning. This viewpoint just matches Japanese cultural “the

beauty of remained blank” by coincidence, that is the incomplete and clumsy pursued by Zen, therefore many Japanese artistic creations all have unfinished or even blank leaving phenomena, this phenomena generates the openness of aesthetic, just as the text inviting structure addressed by Wolfgang Iser, he thought literature self only provides a framework, whether it is on which face or level this framework would leave some “blank”, waits for reader to fill and complete during reading. Aesthetic of reception was originally applied on the aesthetic experience within literature domain, however this content meaning actually matches with design context, and its Western ideal also appears in Eastern design, therefore apply it to the interpretation and transliteration of aesthetic pleasure.

△Figure 1 : Correspondence of literary communication & design communication (Iser, 1978)

△Figure 2 : Aesthetic pleasure framework (Jauss, 1982)

Hans Robert Jauss addressed that the core of aesthetic experience is pleasure, including creation (poiesis) , perception (aesthesis) , and purification (catharsis) , he indicated that creation is the producing level of aesthetic experience, user can generate pleasure and create expression through beauty appreciation process; perception is the acceptance level of aesthetic experience, emphasizes on the pleasant experience generated by emotional cognition; purification is the interchange result generated by beauty appreciation behavior, which is spiritual enhancement and behavior reform after body and mind are touched. Therefore, with the viewpoint of

receptional aesthetic addressed by Hans Robert Jauss, further analyze the aesthetic pleasure within design, can be deduced into creation is to generate aesthetic experience, which is design characterization; perception is the emotion with pleasant vision and hearing after receptional acceptance, which is design cognition; purification is the interchange result of aesthetic experience, from which to understand the modeling of taste and style. In General, aesthetic pleasure differs on cultural, generates various design characterization, however, catering to globalized cultural interchange, from which can also generate new interpretation after cultures are integrated. Thus this study applies the 3 frameworks of Hans Robert Jauss' aesthetic of reception: creation, perception and purification as the 3 frameworks of aesthetic pleasure, and uses practical design cases to compare the difference of Eastern and Western on aesthetic pleasure.

Comparison between Eastern and Western aesthetic pleasure

Generally, Western culture tends to “logical think, rational, left brain, analysis, against nature and materialism, is obvious “intellectual” viewpoint, also is instrumentalism; while Eastern is considered as “fuzzy think, emotional, right brain, converge, compromise nature and spiritualism, that is emphasizes on emotional “perception”. Although only view it normally, but not overall phenomena, however the division of this dualism also significantly shows that cultural difference influences body and spiritual expression, moreover also influences design things' characterization, therefore with creation, perception and purification faces of Hans Robert Jauss' receptional aesthetic, it is able to find difference in between.

Creation

“Creation” is to produce aesthetic experience, that is design characterization, from the above mentioned key difference emphasized by Eastern and Western, can find characterization difference, particularly Japan applies Zen as standard of belief, naturally its beauty interpretation is different to Western, like the word often used by Japanese “kirei” (Scott, 1999) is an adjective of beauty, but it yet has supplementary meanings: clean, neat, good order, which are close to English word “nice”, therefore Japanese life viewpoint of Zen beauty influences many Japanese utensils' characterization. In scholar writings of different nationalities, like Taiwanese Huang Tien-Lin(1995) and Korean well know literary author Lee O-Yong (1998) , all pointed out that the design difference between the East and the West lies in the form corresponding to multifunction and mono-function, like Japanese designer Ekuan(Evans, 1991) used “Furoshiki”, that is the

functional form of packing cloth, with “furoshikibility” a English word of Furoshiki originality, to describe the obvious characterization of the East on design thinking, because Furoshiki is a diversified product form of multifunction, it can pack books, clothes, presents or carry-on, and can be folded and put into pocket after using, quite convenient , this is the adaptability pursued by Zen. On the contrast, Western carry-on packing things such purse, schoolbag or knapsack are usually of mono-function or purpose, can find that the multifunctional form of design openness such as Furoshiki, has extreme flexibility of design openness, can change form into various appearances to cater with users, with both usability and identification of tools, also with usage form of openness.

△Figure 3: Correspondence of multifunction and mono-function

Eastern multifunctional design form, not only Furoshiki, also like sliding door is the combination of window and curtain, chopsticks is the combination of knife and fork, while Huang Tien-Lin and Japanese scholar Hisashi (2000), or even French symbol master Roland Barthes (1992), all used chopsticks and knife and fork to describe the difference of Eastern and Western instrumentalism, because chopsticks not only can clip, but also can cut, stick, split as well as convey food, and these 2 parallel sticks do not have orientation, allow users to use freely as they want, to achieve usage pleasure. Contrarily, Western tools' characteristics usually is of fixed usage, individual functional demand requires independent tool, therefore as to the purpose can be achieved by Eastern chopsticks, Western needs the pairing of 2 tools, knife and fork, so as to achieve it, meanwhile in order to meet the operation convenience of left or right hand, need to divide into dedicated dining utensils designs. It shows that Eastern instrumentalism is user-oriented, with multifunction as demand, design emphasis tends to software planning, design architecture is non-fixed form, can change functional form during using, has extremely large creation space. Contrarily, Western instrumentalism is product-oriented, with mono-function as demand, design emphasis tends to fixed form, usage condition is for specific function and purpose, so everyone use the same functional form, can see Western instrumentalism still emphasizes on materialism.

▼Table 1: Difference between Eastern and Western Design Thinking

	Design orientation	Function demand	Design emphasis	Design architecture	Usage condition
The East	User	Multifunction	Software	Non-fixed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can change functional form • with creation space of openness
The West	Product	Mono- function	Hardware	Fixed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicate to specific function and purpose • Everyone's usage is the same

An anecdote about Newton would perfectly describe this phenomena, he raised a large cat and a small cat, in order to let these 2 cats in and out conveniently, he opened a large hole and a small hole on the same door, to let these 2 cats in and out conveniently, but if from Eastern thinking, open a large hole would be adequate to let these 2 cats in and out, however Newton is a standard Western, his initial principle is the same to the concept of knife and fork. Because of this orientation, there is some difference between Eastern and Western thinking, Western always design out tools dedicated to left or right hand, like fork, knife and spoon, or pens used specifically by left or right hand, but such design seldom appears on Eastern tools, at least no chopsticks are dedicated to left or right hand. While like Japanese traditional clog, is also a design with no division for left or right foot, because they think they may put time and spirit on important and beautiful things and it is not necessary to be particular about trifle for the adaptability of things' orientation.

Therefore, in 1970 Colombo designed an alarm clock named "optic" for Alessi, it showed insistency on fixed design architecture. Generally, when alarm clock is ringing, most users would be busy in looking for switch, hope to stop alarm ringing immediately, however when Colombo was designing this type of alarm clock, a little trouble is made, that is user must put point finger into a small hole, so as to successfully touch the switch button, this might cause sleepy user to wake up easily because of concentrating on putting finger through hole. Moreover, this round hole was opened on the top of hour hand, which just aptly matched with time display (hour hand shape opened a small and hollow out round hole), therefore Colombo's design always make user smile with understanding because of emotional characterization.

△Figure 4: “Optic” alarm clock by Colombo

Perception

Perception is the emotion with pleasant vision and hearing after reception acceptance as well as design cognition. Japanese designer Toshiyuki Kita (2002) proposed the concept of “The soul of design”, he believes that people pay long time attention on the focus of form and function, but he added in third design key element: soul, might be based on the concept of Japanese animism, therefore Toshiyuki Kita thinks that, things must have soul so as to let user treat it with heart, as well as let things not only have practicability but also have value, even though it is damaged later, it still can be repaired with care and continue to use. After all, design art is creative behavior, we must keep perceptual balance between material and spiritual worlds, human and nature, and this is also Japanese typical harmonious aesthetic viewpoint. Particularly Japanese traditional aesthetic is different from Western viewpoint in terms of artistic form of characterization, states that fine art and craft can not have difference, and can not separate with art from daily life, therefore Japanese artistic form is not stated in splendid palace, but must tightly relate to daily life. So, like ceramic master Mori Masahiro who created many utensils of Japanese Hakusan ceramic, he was good at observing user’s using experience, found inspiration from daily life, and constantly shaped brand new style terminology of ceramic work pieces, and therefore, Japanese design field adopted Mori Masahiro’s name “Morism” to represent the spirit of Japanese food utensils. Furthermore, both Japanese and Scandinavian designs have beauty of peace, and evaporate craft and daily appliances within common people’s culture to the extreme, all are near to Zen’s concise, cool and order, while both love to use natural materials. So that, within design perception, both keeps perceptual balance between material and spiritual worlds, human and nature.

△Figure 5: Silent design about Masahiro Mori' (left) and Scandinavian tableware (right)

Many Japanese utensils' designs especially emphasize on hand touching, this can not be attractive to people by the quality sense generated by modern machine production, due to often use natural materials such as paper, wood, bamboo, and rattan, after human hand touching or using, presents with special and natural formed traces, so as to add in the emotional interchange and integrated contact of users, even though same things are bought, but because of natural texture difference, and traces left after using, they present special affection which is hard to replace, just like Japanese well known literary author Junichiro Tanizaki (1977) thought of Chinese jade, its luster comes from human hand touching over years, thus massaged at the same place repeatedly, greasy dirt and sweat penetrate into it to present special luster, belongs to Eastern special grace and taste, that is the naturally formed surface trace through hand dirt touching, and this is *sabi*, means green rust, patina, a pattern of deposition over years, differs to Western aesthetic of phototropism and clean pursuing, like the way the West treat metallic utensils such as silverware, what is appreciated is the surface quality sense of extreme brightness, but Japanese insist on appreciating the traces of rust and human hand touching presented over time accumulation. This might be like the "roughness" mentioned by Japanese folk art master Yanagi (1993), Astringent, is typical Eastern beauty, that is in the extreme 10 points, only express 8 point while reserve 2 points, and this 2 points can express implicit and silent beauty, is a kind of deep, solid remitting Eastern beauty.

△Figure 6 : Astringent- A typical Eastern beauty

Purification

Purification is the interchange result of aesthetic experience, from which can understand the modeling of taste and style. Although the East and the West deal frequently, even the East frequently worships Western culture, however, Eastern cultural context with deep philosophical

thinking is quite attractive to the West. In terms of extreme simple style, Eastern presentation often comes from the fulfillment of life thinking, like the fundamental spirit of Zen observed by Japanese, emphasizes on “empty, nil” artistic conception, from which to express appreciation and usage viewpoint on utensils; while viewing from the West from fundamentalism of functionalism, emphasizes on “less is more” low limitation style, deems decoration as iniquity. If observe the pure aesthetic conveyed by Japan and Scandinavian, in addition to the difference of life thinking and regional culture, is the concealed essential thinking conveyed by the highly developed design. As to pure beauty, both Japan and Scandinavian have relevant words to describe it, such as word “hygge” , came from Danish, means “peace, comfortable, smooth feelings”, while in Japanese is “wabi-sabi” plain aesthetic, simple and harmony are closest to its spiritual meaning, but wabi-sabi concept came from Zen, Buddhism concept, therefore in addition to simple form, its characterization aesthetic is sort of “imperfect, temporary, broken and incomplete” meaning.

△Figure7: Wabi-sabi and hygge

Many Japanese designs often present “no design” cool characteristics of eliminating waste and keeping essence, at first look, there is no affection at all, but this interpretation of things’ interface, is Japanese traditional aesthetic “ma”, that is beauty of blank leaving, echoing to Toshiyuki Kita’s third key element of design: soul, only that soul is not designer’s complete interpretation, a little similar to “roughness” concept, express 8 points, reserve 2 points, and this 2 points is the self interpretation part shaped under the interaction of user and things. Just like Issey Miyake said: “I have never completed my own production, because it is only half done, another half can only be accomplished by the costume wearer,” so this type of unfinished design concept, led to design openness, allow wearer to participate in incomplete status. Another designer Rei Kawakubo often presents threads left at seams, but aptly shape special style interpretation, especially when common people first contact Rei Kawakubo’s costume, usually unable to identify the positions of neckline and sleeve cuff, completely breaks up common

people's identification on costume functionality, also because of functional ambiguity, creates unique and unordinary style, so that modern Japanese designers routinely present deconstruct costume form, result in new aesthetic styles.

△Figure 8 : Rei Kawakubo (left) and Issey Miyake's Design (A-POC) (right)

Probably the East has been deeply rinsed by Zen thinking, therefore many utensil designs follow “adaptability” property, such as Issey Miyake’s “A-POC” series, is an extension of kimono’s one piece of cloth concept, not limited by the height and height of wearer, only manipulate with waist belt, adapt to human body figure, and A-POC series even evaporate diversified one piece of cloth concept, tailor on wearing, no need of sewing, because Issey Miyake only provides special fabrics and basic shape, costume style is completely determined by wearer. However, the West pays more attention to result, so as to be easily limited on form, result in closeness and singleness of design, maybe Eastern life viewpoint is temporary, while the West is always permanent, thus led to the aesthetic form difference between them, just like Japanese designers usually mention word emptiness, such as Hara Kenya said empty container is to replace message, hope receiving party can fill in implication to complete communication. Just like Chuangzi’s famous dictum “a place of nothing” (Hara, 2005), things looked useless at first look, its content is rather plentiful, because only empty container is possible for storing, right because of undefined possibility result in plenty of diversified interpretations. And such viewpoint just like half cup of water, to Western people it is inadequate condition, but to Eastern people it is just right, because it has space for filling into implication.

Conclusion

From the 3 frameworks of reception aesthetic addressed by Robert Jauss: creation, perception, and purification, to probe into the instrumentalism difference between the East and the West, while upon the globalized frequent deals and even cultural integration, what has been presented by Eastern and Western aesthetic pleasure is not the comparison resulted from complete cutting, but rather is under cultural subject, with local cultural characteristics, and with some more

cross-cultural or even borderless design interests. Therefore the 3 faces of reception aesthetic addressed by Robert Jauss, was originally to discuss the interaction interface of experience aesthetic between author text creation and reader, is applied on the aesthetic pleasure exploration of design communication, that is on the aesthetic pleasure interface when designer creates things and users' inter-communication, can clarify the context of design characterization and perception. This study is only an initial exploration, in the future will use this viewpoint as basis to conduct further analysis and discussion, in order to perform wider research exploration about aesthetic pleasure.

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